

Job Competencies of Employees: Basis for a Capability Building Plan

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Abstract:

Competence is needed to deal with rapid environmental changes. The sustainability of an organization can be maintained depending on the organization's ability to adapt to change. Thus, this study aimed to determine the job competencies of employees in a government agency during the fiscal year 2023 as basis for a capability-building plan. Descriptive research design was employed in determining the level of job competencies of 46 employee-respondents. A valid and reliability-tested researcher-made questionnaire and the standardized Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) were used to gather data in this study. The first part of the questionnaire dealt with the respondents' profile while second part focused on their job competencies in self-management, professionalism and ethics, result focus, teamwork, service orientation, and innovation. Profiles of the respondents are mostly older, male, longer in service, and in the lower positions. Data revealed that most employees have high level of competencies in the areas of self-management, result focus, teamwork, service orientation, and innovation. A deviation in the area of professionalism and ethics was noticeable, wherein from a high level to very high level of competence, emerged. Furthermore, a significant difference showed in the employees' level of competencies in the areas of self-management, professionalism and ethics, result focus, and teamwork based on groupings by plantilla position. These findings call for the Department heads to provide explicit standards that will guide the employees in their work to improve their competency levels.

Keywords: Job competencies, self-management, professionalism and ethics, result focus, teamwork, service orientation, innovation.

Introduction:

Nature of Problem

Job competency is necessary for government employees. They are required to be able to provide optimal services to the community and become reliable human resources in carrying out their duties and must be able to carry out a mental revolution that demands a commitment to serve the community to create good governance.

Following this philosophy, the Department of Education (DepEd) employs a Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS). It is a joint undertaking between the superior and the employee that allows for an open discussion of job expectations, key results areas, objectives, and how they relate to overarching departmental goals. It provides performance standards and behaviors that promote professional and personal growth within the organization (DepEd memo, Order No. 2, series of 2015) and to guarantee that employees work efficiently, on time, and with quality as stipulated in the Civil Service Commission Memorandum Circular No. 6, s. 2012, or the Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS). The Domains of the RPMS are captured by the competencies that determine employee quality in the country. Teamwork skills, participation, overcomers, resourcefulness, and the ability to work with little supervision are all displayed by the employee. Service orientation is the process by which employees explain organizational pathways, assume accountability for customer service, advocate for empowerment, enhance workplace vision, and implement service improvement programs. Innovation is the process by which employees identify causes of problems and suggest workable solutions, promote creative thinking, increase productivity, and cultivate a creative environment. It entails applying resource constraints creatively, strengthening organizational and workplace power, and strengthening work environments.

On the other hand, the current challenge the DepEd Central Office faces is the competence of employees. According to Human Resources Department data, 41% of its employees did not meet the Department's competencies (Corpin, 2022). They frequently struggle to fulfill the RPMS's skills as effectively and efficiently as they could, which has led to a decline in their capacity to lead, low staff morale, increased absenteeism, bad employee citizenship behavior, and subpar organizational performance. Additionally, a number of DepEd workers lack the knowledge and abilities necessary to perform their jobs with professionalism and competence. These workers must be qualified, competent, effective, and efficient. Unfortunately, the public's perception of Department

bureaucracy seems to be that it fosters complex, ambiguous performance, lacks clear guidelines, and contains aspects of nepotism, collusion, and corruption.

These bureaucratic problems have likewise become an obstacle to realizing bureaucratic reform in the Department, which also makes bureaucratic reform in the Philippines unable to comply with the concept of good governance. The community would still assess the Department that there are delays in convoluted procedures, is slow, or requires additional costs and takes a long time and other things to do when processing something at a government office. This fact should be an essential concern to make changes following the demands and development of society.

The current job competencies among DepEd employees must be changed or reformed. Every individual in the Department must have high integrity, function productively, be accountable, have a professional attitude, and guard his/her behavior toward following the code of ethics and the oath of office for the benefit of the nation and society. Job competence needs to be done objectively by looking at the competency targets, with evidence of their mastery of Self-Management, Professionalism and Ethics, Result Focus, Teamwork, Service Orientation, and Innovation to be able to achieve increasing efficiency, effectiveness, and responsiveness to improve organizational performance. Thus, the proponent, as the current Supervising Administrative Officer in the General Service Division, suggests that there should be an assessment of employees' competencies to provide responsive training to enhance their competencies and maintain harmonious human relations.

Current State of Knowledge

Job competences are critical in the management of activities involving each individual's authority to carry out duties or make choices in accordance with their role in the organization, which is relevant to their expertise, knowledge, and talents. Competency is essential in managing government activities that require professionalism and work ethics. Government employees are required to provide optimal services to the community and become reliable human resources in carrying out their duties as government representatives. They must be able to carry out a mental revolution that demands a commitment to serve the community in order to create good governance (De Zoysa, 2022).

There is a demand for every organization, especially public organizations, to achieve results with optimal use of time and resources yet still provide the best possible service to the community. Result focus as competency is the primary key that must be considered (Zenger, 2019). Result-focused employee focuses on results and desired outcomes and how best to achieve them (Folkman, 2022). Performance statement of a result-focused employee sets high goals and works tenaciously to achieve them (Potnuru et al., 2020), pushes self and others to reach milestones (Avery & Murphy, 2018), looks for opportunities to help move a project along (Bohlander et al., 2021), volunteers to help others with projects or assignments (Hashim, 2018), sees when analysis and discussion have served their purpose and moves to action (Heinsman et al., 2018), responds to setbacks with renewed and increased efforts (Lawson & Limbrick, 2016), is persistent in the face of difficulty (Jepson, 2015), willingly puts in extra time and effort, especially in time of crises (Lucia, & Lepsinger, (2019), goes the "extra mile" to ensure the goal is met (Medlin & Green, 2019).

The job competencies of an organization and its influence in the community invariably depend on the kind of employees working in it. For government offices, Dahlström et al. (2021) argue that the existence of bureaucratic problems will become an obstacle to realizing bureaucratic reform, and this would be unable to comply with the concept of good governance. The community would still assess that there are delays in convoluted procedures, is slow, or requires additional costs and takes a long time and other things to do when processing something at a government office (Asree et al., 2020). This fact should be an essential concern for bureaucratic reform in order to make changes following the demands and development of society (Cordella & Tempini, 2015). Of course, these bureaucratic problems must be changed or reformed. Thus, competency in service orientation must be expected of all employees.

Competent government employees throughout their careers demonstrate the following professional attributes: Core behavioral competency (i.e., Self-Management, Professionalism and Ethics, Result Focus, Teamwork, Service Orientation, and Innovation); and core skills (i.e., Achievement, Managing Diversity, and Accountability). Nicdao (2021) contends that the capacity to self-manage through adaptation and flexibility in the face of change is another aspect of emotional competence that a person might exhibit. According to Franco (2020), knowledge—which denotes expertise in a certain field—is a crucial component of competence, which is necessary to achieve self-management. Moreover, Anonuevo (2020) expresses that self-management competency exhibits the ability to understand conditions in detail and think systematically (analytical thinking). This means that one must be able to see conditions in the workplace carefully and in detail and think or analyze properly to determine what to do in connection with one's job.

Theoretical Underpinnings

Having superior, dependable human resources and competence is one way for any organization to gain a competitive edge. Even with the support of infrastructure, facilities, and abundant funding sources, the organization's activities cannot be carried out properly without the support of dependable human resources. Therefore, in order for the organizational program to carry out effectively, a premium must be placed on employees' competencies. It is not enough for people to dedicate their lives to productivity and life; they also need to know what they are committed to, which is, ideally, establishing a plan for improvement. As a result, competency appraisal's status as an essential human resource function contributing to total quality management cannot be understated.

For this reason, the study is anchored on two Competency theories advanced by Lyle and Spencer (cited in Rahmawati et al., 2018) and McClelland (cited in Diep & Hartmann, 2016). In order to understand competency, Lyle and Spencer (cited in Rahmawati et al., 2018) developed the Iceberg Model to describe competency in two dimensions. These are the more visible (visible, easy to measure and develop), while other dimensions related to a person's personal characteristics tend to be difficult to develop and hidden. Visible competencies are, in fact, only something that almost everyone can learn, so they are only categorized as "threshold competencies" or prerequisite competencies. Competencies that are not visible are "differentiating competencies" or competencies that differentiate between people who perform better than others, consisting of self-concept, traits, and motives.

This was expounded by Prahalad (2021) who organized competencies into three main categories: Core competencies, which refers to behavioral elements that are important for all employees. Leadership/managerial competencies involve competencies associated with leading organizations and people. Functional competencies are job-specific skills needed to perform a specific job or professional role. Thus, competency is the elemental distinctive of a person who is causally related to criterion-referenced as to be impelling and or excellent in performing a job or situation.

The Competence theory advanced by Lyle and Spencer can be linked to the present study because this lays the foundation for understanding the different variables included in DepEd Central Office employees' job competencies, namely Self-Management the ability to plan, organize, and mobilize; Professionalism and Ethics which is the ability to control one's self and show a professional personality at work; Result Focus is the ability to motivate, utilize, and develop human resources; Teamwork is the ability to work together with workers to achieve a common goal; Service Orientation is the ability to perform the role and make use of various resources; and Innovation the ability to visualize the invisible, think at an abstract level, and use thinking to plan the future direction of activities. The theory of Competence Management supported the researcher in her quest to determine the level of competencies of employees, thus establishing the basis for designing a capability-building plan.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the job competencies of employees in a government agency during the fiscal year 2023 as the basis for a capability-building plan. Specifically, it sought to determine: 1) the level of job competencies of employees according to the area of self-management, professionalism and ethics, result focus, teamwork, service orientation, innovation; and 2) the significant difference in the level of job competencies of employees when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Methodology

This section presents the methodology of the study. It discusses the research design, locale of the study, subject and the participants, the data gathering procedure, which includes the research instrument and the test of its validity and reliability, the data-processing procedure, the analytical schemes, and the statistical tools.

Research Design

The study employed the descriptive research design in determining the level of job competencies of employees in a government agency during the fiscal year 2023 as a basis for a capability-building plan. Descriptive design is a type of research design that aims at obtaining information and, thus, systematically describing a particular phenomenon, situation, or population. It helps researchers acquire answers to research questions as to who, what, when, where, and how based on the data collected from the identified respondents with the use of descriptive survey instruments in the collection of data (Nassaji, 2015).

Respondents

The study's respondents were taken from the following Administrative Service Division: Asset Management Division, Cash Division, Records Division, Central Security and Safe Office, and General Services Division.

Currently, there are 249 employees assigned in the said division. Since the number of respondents is quite significant to handle, the study used the stratifying sampling method. This method involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata (Hayes, 2019). Using the Slovin's formula with 105 error of margin, there were 46 employees participated in the study. The percentage of the respondents coming from each department were divided by the total number of respondents and multiplied by the sample size.

Instruments

A researcher-made survey questionnaire and the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) under Core Behavioral Competencies were the main instruments used to gather data in this study. It was subjected to validity (4.52-excellent) and reliability (0.945-excellent). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively. The survey questionnaire was divided into two parts. Part I dealt with the profile of the respondents and part II was the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) under Core Behavioral Competencies which focused on assessing the respondents' job competency in self-management, professionalism and ethics, result focus, teamwork, service orientation, and innovation. IPCRF is a tool for evaluating performance. As per DepEd Order 2, S. 2015 "The Guidelines on the Establishment and Implementation of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) in the Department of Education (DepEd)," it aims to provide comprehensive guidelines for DepEd's adoption of the Civil Service Commission's (CSC) Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS). According to Canoma (2017), the objectives listed are the duties and responsibilities that every government employee must perform while in service. This is a method for determining whether someone is performing their tasks diligently, efficiently, and on schedule. There were five questions in each competency area being investigated. To measure the extent of perception, the following scale was used: 1 -very low level; 2- low level; 3- moderate level; 4- high level; and 5- very high level.

Data-Gathering Procedure

To achieve the objective of the study, a step-by-step procedure for gathering data was used. The first step was to seek the approval of the Assistant Secretary for Administration by sending a letter of permission for the conduct of the study. Upon approval, the researcher created the questionnaire, which acted as the study's research instrument. After which, the researcher created a Google form that included all of the test's components and detailed instructions on how to respond to each one. Self-made questionnaires were administered in the departments included in this study. The researcher discussed and described the content, purpose, and survey instructions, and then gave the link to the Google Form to the respondents, who were asked to forward it to the researcher. Respondents were given a full week to complete the surveys. Thereafter, the assigned statistician gathered, checked, encoded, and interpreted questionnaires with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS).

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 also used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of job competencies of employees in terms of self-management, professionalism and ethics, result focus, teamwork, service orientation, and innovation. Objective No. 2 used the comparative analytical scheme and the Mann-Whitney U test to unfold the significant difference in the level of job competencies of the respondents when they are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Ethical Considerations

The study was carried out in accordance to the ethical requirements of scientific practices and of the law (Data Protection Act of 1998). The researcher requested the respondents' freely informed consent. The interviewees' identities were never divulged during the survey. This contained the identity and other personal information about their family and/or relatives. Throughout the research, every attempt was taken to uphold high ethical standards. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained at all times.

Results and Discussions

This section comprises the gathered data based on the researcher's study objectives. The analysis and interpretation of data were presented in tabular form, along with the study results' implications.

Table 1
Level of Job Competencies of Employees in Self-management

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Sets personal goals and direction, needs and development.	4.10	High Level
2. Undertakes personal actions and behaviors that are clear and purposive	4.15	High Level

and takes into account personal goals and values congruent to that of the organization.

3. Displays emotional maturity and enthusiasm for and is challenged by higher goals.	4.10	High Level
4. To achieve goals, Prioritize work tasks and schedules (through Gantt charts, checklists, etc.).	4.04	High Level
5. Set high-quality, challenging, realistic goals for self and others.	4.06	High Level
Mean	4.09	High Level

Table 1 displays employees' job competency level in the area of Self-Management. The employee-respondents believed their competency level in this area was high. This is indicated in the overall mean of 4.09. This corroborates the study of Strauss et al. (2017) that self-management as a competency is regarded as the motivational factor of individuals and may push them to pursue a positive identity at work. From the data presented, it can be deduced that item 2, obtained the highest mean of 4.15. This suggests that each respondent can highly see conditions in the workplace carefully and in detail and be able to think or analyze properly to determine what to do in connection with his or her job. Moreover, item 4 had the lowest mean of 4.04. This implies that employees are unable to apply systematic methods to prioritize their job tasks and timelines. According to Nufus (2018), government employees must be able to endure a mental revolution to give optimal services to the community and become trusted human resources when carrying out their tasks as government representatives.

Table 2
Level of Job Competencies of Employees in Professionalism and Ethics

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Demonstrates the values and behavior enshrined in the Norms of Conduct and Ethical Standards for public officials and employees (RA 6713).	4.32	High Level
2. Practices ethical and professional behavior and conduct, considering the impact of his/her actions and decisions.	4.30	High Level
3. Maintains a professional image: trustworthy, regular attendance and punctuality, good grooming, and communication.	4.30	High Level
4. Make personal sacrifices to meet the organization's needs.	3.91	High Level
5. Acts with a sense of urgency and responsibility to meet the organization's needs, improve systems, and help others improve their effectiveness.	4.15	High Level
Mean	4.20	High Level

Table 2 describes the level of job competency of employees in the area of professionalism and ethics. It reveals that the overall mean is 4.20, and it is at a high level. It is important to note that among the items, item 1 obtained the highest mean of 4.32 while item 4 obtain the lowest mean of 3.91. This shows that the employees are unwilling to make personal sacrifices; they lack self-sacrificial behavior at work. This could be due to a lack of resources or domestic discord. According to Paler (2018), professionalism and ethics require commitment, motivation, and dedication in reaching the highest performance standard and achieving results in support of the organization's mandate. Navarro (2017) also emphasized that professionalism and ethics necessitates making sacrifices particularly in decision-making. However, it should be in consultation with the pertinent managerial level and in full compliance with the organization's regulations, rules, and policies. Given this, department heads should take a closer look at this behavior to better understand it as a potential explanatory variable for enhancing their competencies.

Table 3
Level of Job Competencies of Employees in Result-focus

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Achieves results with optimal use of time and resources most of the time.	4.15	High Level
2. Avoids rework, mistakes, and wastage through effective work methods by placing organizational needs before personal needs.	4.13	High Level
3. Delivers error-free outputs most of the time by conforming to standard operating procedures correctly and consistently. Able to produce very satisfactory quality of work in terms of usefulness/acceptability and completeness with no supervision required.	3.95	High Level
4. Expresses a desire to improve and may express frustration at waste or inefficiency. May focus on new or more precise ways of meeting goals set.	4.02	High Level
5. Makes specific changes in the system or in own work methods to improve performance. Examples may include doing something better, faster, at a lower cost, more efficiently, or improving quality, customer satisfaction, and morale without setting any specific goal.	4.10	High Level

Mean 4.07 **High Level**

Disclosed in Table 3 is the level of job competency of employees in the area of Result Focus. The employees generally believed they have a high level in this area, as it recorded an overall mean of 4.07. This suggests that result-focused employee focuses on results and desired outcomes and how best to achieve them. Additionally, the data reveals that item 1 typically accomplishes results with the best use of time and resources, obtaining the highest mean of 4.15 while item 3 was assessed to be the lowest mean of 3.95 and both interpreted as high level. This suggests that employees find to be struggling in identifying roles, responsibilities, and expected outcomes within their department's or division's program. This is the primary area of skill that the department head must consider. One way to achieve this is through their results in achieving tasks in the context of the organization's program, seeking guidance and feedback on their performance, responding appropriately, and taking action to improve the results achieved, evaluating their results objectively, reviewing targets and applying the lessons learned, following instructions received concerning official duties, and complies with the organization. According to Pamintuan's (2017) study, employees should also receive training that includes efforts for identifying realistic outputs and clarifying roles, responsibilities, and expected outcomes within the context of the department's or division's program.

Table 4

Level of Job Competencies of Employees in Teamwork

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Willingly does his/her share of responsibility.	4.43	High Level
2. Promotes collaboration and removes barriers to teamwork and goal accomplishment across the organization.	4.19	High Level
3. Applies negotiation principles in arriving at win-win agreements.	4.02	High Level
4. Drives consensus and team ownership of decisions.	3.93	High Level
5. Works constructively and collaboratively with others and across organizations to accomplish organizational goals and objectives.	4.19	High Level
Mean	4.15	High Level

The employees' perceptions of the level of job competency in Teamwork are presented in Table 4. Generally, the employee-respondents believed they had a high level of competency in this area, as shown by the mean of 4.15. This implies that they have a good sense of teamwork on the course of action to be taken or chosen to lead to achieving the Department's objectives or goals. In the same view, item 1 obtained the highest mean of 4.43 interpreted as high level. This suggests they can promote team cooperation and commitment to achieve goals and deliverable. However, item 4 obtained the lowest mean of 3.93 (high level). This suggests that employees fell short on encouraging team unity through sharing information or expertise and working together to solve problems. According to Aguinis & Kraiger (2019), Le et al. (2020), Hussain and Mohtar (2016), and Klein (2020), the performance statement of teamwork should ensure joint ownership of goal setting, commitments, and accomplishments, and involve everyone on the team. The result of this study may be useful to the department heads in that they may consider encouraging the employees to foster cooperation and dedication within a team to achieve goals and deliverables (Keban, 2018).

Table 5

Level of Job Competencies of Employees in Service Orientation

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Explains and articulates organizational directions, issues, and problems.	4.02	High Level
2. Takes personal responsibility for dealing with and/or correcting customer service issues and concerns.	4.15	High Level
3. Initiates activities that promote advocacy for men's and women's empowerment.	3.63	High Level
4. Participates in updating office vision, mission, mandates, and strategies based on DepEd strategies and directions.	3.91	High Level
5. Develop and adopt service improvement programs through simplified procedures to enhance service delivery.	4.10	High Level
Mean	3.96	High Level

Exhibited in Table 5 is the level of job competency of the employees in the area of Service Orientation. The employee's degree of proficiency in this area is typically high (3.96). This implies that the staff members have developed strong bonds with the clients in order to comprehend and satisfy or surpass their needs. In this sense, the respondents outline the characteristics as essential to effective public servants. The data also shows that item 2

had the highest mean of 4.15 (high level), which was also the highest score. This shows that the staff members respect open communication, maintain a friendly workplace, and are approachable. On the other hand, item 3 obtained the lowest mean of 3.63 (high level). This result implies that the employees were less likely initiate actions that encourage men's and women's support towards well-being. Empowerment and sex equality are viewed as critical components of accomplishing sustainable development goals. At the same time, empowerment among sex is a transformational process that enables the employees to develop the capacity to decide and act on life choices. In this regard, the result may be useful to head departments to come up with effective information about empowerment through collaboration and interdependence. It should also inform the employees that empowerment is multifaceted and requires an intersectional approach wherein incorporating men into women empowerment projects in a department that supports to address inherent structures of sex inequalities. These findings are in line with previous suggestions that government employees should initiate activities that promote advocacy for men and women empowerment (Chenet et al., 2020). Rodriguez (2016) declares teamwork regarding competence as a social behavior approach which includes the existence of social awareness of how to relate to others, feelings, needs, and concerns for others.

Table 6
Level of Job Competencies of Employees in Innovation

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Examine the root cause of problems and suggest effective solutions. Fosters new ideas processes, and suggests better ways to do things (cost and/or operational efficiency).	4.04	High Level
2. Demonstrates an ability to think "beyond the box". Continuously focuses on improving personal productivity to create higher value and results.	3.95	High Level
3. Promotes a creative climate and inspires co-workers to develop original ideas or solutions.	3.89	High Level
4. Translates creative thinking into tangible changes and solutions that improve the work unit and organization.	3.93	High Level
5. Uses ingenious methods to accomplish responsibilities. Demonstrates resourcefulness and the ability to succeed with minimal resources.	3.95	High Level
Mean	3.95	High Level

Table discloses the results of employees' job competency level in the area of Innovation with an overall mean of 3.95 (high level). Rigor (2019) conforms that acquiring innovation skills increases the employee's competency.

It is worth noting that among the items, item 1 obtained the highest mean of 4.04 (high level). This suggests that the employees have a sense of innovation. They acquire and apply new skills to remain up-to-date in his/her area of expertise. In addition, they can reliably apply knowledge and propose new procedures and techniques in response to changing needs in each area of their work. However, item 3 obtained the lowest mean of 3.89 (high level). This result suggests that not all employees consider the opportunity to exchange knowledge and information with peers and colleagues. The result conforms to Allejo (2018) in exploring the factors that contributed to or hindered team learning in the innovation process. With the above rating, there is an impression that department heads should seek strategies wherein the employees would have the means to systematically exercise their innovation capableness toward achieving a competitive advantage in response to the changing needs of the time.

Table 7
Difference in the Level of Job Competencies of Employees in the area Self-management When Grouped According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	21	25.45	221.500	0.361	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	25	21.86				
Sex	Male	25	23.40	260.000	0.956	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	21	23.62				
Plantilla Position	Lower	32	20.09	115.000	0.009	0.05	Significant
	Higher	14	31.29				

Length of Service	Shorter	19	27.47	181.000	0.089	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	27	20.70				

Table 7 reveals the difference in the level of job competency in the area self-management when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. The data shows that all the variables except the variable plantilla position have no significant difference in job competency as assessed by the employees in self-management. The general result implies that the employees' views on the level of job competency in terms of self-management were almost similar across demographic categories. Also, results shows that plantilla position has influenced the level of job competency of the employees in self-management. This may be due to the fact that majority of the study's respondents are operational staff members who are in charge of carrying out directives from leaders and are therefore not granted additional authority to carry out activities initiated at their discretion. The study of Orbino (2018) revealed No significant difference in the variable age, sex, length of service, and employees' ranking in the area of Self-Management. This conforms the findings of this study. However, in Plantilla Position, the result of the study of Orbino (2018) negates the finding of this study.

Table 8
Difference in the Level of Job Competencies of Employees in Professionalism and Ethics When Grouped According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	21	23.55	261.500	0.982	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	25	23.46				
Sex	Male	25	22.26	231.500	0.488	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	21	24.98				
Plantilla Position	Lower	32	19.73	103.500	0.004	0.05	Significant
	Higher	14	32.11				
Length of Service	Shorter	19	26.03	208.500	0.278	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	27	21.72				

Table 8 reveals that there is no significant difference in job competency assessed by the employees in professionalism and ethics when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables except for plantilla position. Results imply that position in the department likely does affect the employees' ability to perform their job professionally and ethically. These results suggest that the employees rated their competency in professionalism and ethics almost similarly regardless of their group categories. It infers that the demographic profile of the employees was not a determinant of their perceptions. In other words, the employees' age, sex, and length of service will not matter to how the employees see their job competencies in the department. However, as per plantilla position, it has somehow affected the employees' perception regarding professionalism and ethics. The study of Ferrell et al. (2022), result revealed No significant difference in the variables age, sex, and number of years in service in the area of Professionalism and Ethics. This conforms the findings of this study. However, in Plantilla Position, the study negates the finding of this study.

Table 9
Difference in the Level of Job Competencies of Employees in Result Focus When Grouped According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	21	24.40	243.500	0.673	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	25	22.74				
Sex	Male	25	23.20	255.000	0.868	0.05	Not Significant

	Female	21	23.86				
Plantilla Position	Lower	32	20.84	139.000	0.041	0.05	Significant
	Higher	14	29.57				
Length of Service	Shorter	19	27.21	186.000	0.113	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	27	20.89				

Table 9 discloses the significant difference in the level of job competencies as assessed by the employees in the area of result focus when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Based on the data, no significant difference is noted in the level of job competency in teamwork when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables except for the plantilla position. Furthermore, these results imply that the employees' perceptions of their competency in terms of result focus do not differ regardless of age, sex and length of service. This shows that the employees' insights were not affected by their group profiles, and their opinions were independent of the aforementioned variables. On the other hand, the employees' plantilla position, which obtained a u-test score of 139.000 and a p-value of 0.041 lesser than the alpha of 0.05, did show a significant difference in the context of result focus. The study of Marquez (2022) revealed No significant difference in the variable age, sex, and length of service in the area of Results-Focus. This conforms the findings of this study. However, in Plantilla Position, the study negates the finding of this study.

Table 10

Difference in the Level of Job Competencies of Employees in Teamwork When Grouped According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	21	24.71	237.000	0.569	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	25	22.48				
Sex	Male	25	21.28	207.000	0.215	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	21	26.14				
Plantilla Position	Lower	32	20.73	135.500	0.032	0.05	Significant
	Higher	14	29.82				
Length of Service	Shorter	19	26.34	202.500	0.222	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	27	21.50				

Table 10 shows the significant difference in the level of job competencies as assessed by the employees in teamwork when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Based on the data, no significant difference is noted in the level of job competency in teamwork when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables aside from plantilla position. This implies that the plantilla position of the employees has affected their competence towards teamwork. These results suggest that the employees rated their job competency in terms of teamwork similarly in age, sex, and length of service categories. It infers that these demographic profiles of the employees are a determinant of their perceptions. In other words, employees' age, sex, and length of service will not matter how employees see their competencies in teamwork. On the other hand, the employees' perceptions were affected by their position, and their opinions were dependent on the aforementioned variable. The study of Kozlowski and Ilgen (2017), revealed no significant difference in the variable age, sex, and length of service in the area of Teamwork. This conforms the findings of this study. However, in Plantilla Position, the study negates the finding of this study.

Table 11

Difference in the Level of Job Competencies of Employees in Service Orientation When Grouped According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
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Age	Younger	21	25.67	217.000	0.310	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	25	21.68				
Sex	Male	25	23.76	256.000	0.885	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	21	23.19				
Plantilla Position	Lower	32	23.34	219.000	0.904	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	14	23.86				
Length of Service	Shorter	19	23.18	250.500	0.892	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	27	23.72				

Table 11 discloses the significant difference in job competencies assessed by the employees in service orientation when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. The results reveal no significant difference in job competencies as assessed by the employees in service orientation when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. This result implies that the employees' perceptions of their job competencies regarding service orientation do not differ regardless of age, sex, plantilla position, and length of service. Also, this shows that the employees' insights were not affected by their group profiles, and their opinions were independent of the aforementioned variables. The study of Brady and Cronin (2018), result revealed No significant difference in the variables age, sex, plantilla position, and length of service in the area of Service Orientation. This conforms the findings the finding of this study.

Table 12

Difference in the Level of Job Competencies of Employees in Innovation When Grouped According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	21	26.17	206.500	0.211	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	25	21.26				
Sex	Male	25	23.68	258.000	0.920	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	21	23.29				
Plantilla Position	Lower	32	24.42	194.500	0.475	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	14	21.39				
Length of Service	Shorter	19	22.11	230.000	0.549	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	27	24.48				

Table 12 shows the significant difference in the level of job competencies of the employees in innovation when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Based on the data, no significant difference is noted in the level of job competencies in innovation when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. The result may suggest that the employees' age, sex, plantilla position and length of service do not directly affect their competence to be innovative. The study of Tamayao (2016), result revealed No significant difference in the variable age, sex, plantilla position, and length of service in the area of Innovation. This conforms the findings the finding of this study.

Conclusions

Based on the analyzed and interpreted data presented in this study, the respondents showed that the level of their job competencies is high, which significantly may have contributed to and influenced the effectiveness of providing optimal services to the community and becoming reliable human resources in carrying out their duties as government representatives. It can be inferred that the job competencies of the employees were seen differently in the lower and higher categories. It also concludes that the job competencies shown by the employees change depending on their profile. It leads to the conclusion that employees differed in assessing their job competencies when grouped according to plantilla position. In other words, their resoluteness may be high, but because more have lower positions, they have limited power that prevents them from executing fully. Therefore, giving the

employees a chance to fully demonstrate their job competencies is an important component in managing activities that concern the authority of each individual to carry out tasks or make decisions according to their role in the organization that is relevant to their expertise, knowledge, and abilities. Overall, the employees are found to have high and adequate competencies as they dispose of their duties and responsibilities as representatives of the government. Based on the conclusions of this study, the following recommendations were drawn: 1) it is recommended that department heads identify self-management behaviors, take a closer look at employees who fail to make personal sacrifices, encourage employees to foster cooperation and dedication within a team, come up with effective information about empowerment through collaboration and interdependence. And 2) Department heads should seek strategies wherein the employees would have the means to systematically exercised their innovation capableness toward achieving a competitive advantage in response to the changing needs of the time.

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References

- Aguinis, H. & Kraiger, K. (2019). Benefits of training and development for individuals and teams, organizations, and society. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 60, 451–474.
- Allejo, M. (2018) Discontinuous innovation and the new product development process. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 15, 304–321.
- Anonuevo, D. (2020). A model of future-oriented motivation and self-regulation. *Educ. Psychol. Rev.* 16, 9–33.
- Asree, S., Zain, M., & Razalli, M. R. (2020). Influence of leadership competency and organizational culture on responsiveness and performance of firms. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 22(4), 500–516.
- Avery, R. D., & Murphy, K. R. (2018). Performance evaluation in work settings. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 49, 141-168.
- Bohlander, G., Snell, S., & Sherman, A. (2021). *Managing human resources*. Australia: South Western College Publishing.
- Brady, M.K. & Cronin, J.J. (2018). Customer orientation: effects on customer service perceptions and outcome behaviors. *Journal of Service Research*, Vol. 3 No. 3, pp. 241-251
- Canoma, M. (2017). The benefit to professional development. *American Educator*, 26(2), 2225.
- Chenet, P., Tynan, C. & Money, A. (2020). The service performance gap: testing the redeveloped causal model. *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 34 Nos 3/4, pp. 472-497.
- Cordella, A., & Tempini, N. (2015). E-government and organizational change: Reappraising the role of ICT and bureaucracy in public service delivery. *Government Information Quarterly*, 32(3), 279–286.
- Corpin, R. (2022). Administrators' evaluation on employees' competence as basis in defining preparation for professional development. Unpublished dissertation. Philippine Normal University.
- Dahlström C., Lapuente, V., & Teorell, J. (2021). The merit of meritocratization: Politics, bureaucracy, and the institutional deterrents of corruption. *Political Research Quarterly*. 2021; 65: 656-668.
- De Zoysa, H. N. (2022). Inculcating Professional Ethics among Employees in the Workplace: A Systematic Literature Review. *January 2022 International Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies* 9(1):21-34.
- Diep, P. C., & Hartmann, M. (2016). Green Skills in Vocational Teacher Education – a model of pedagogical competence for a world of sustainable development. *TVET@Asia*, (6), 1–19.
- Ferrell, O. C., Fraedrich, J., & Ferrell, L. (2022). Inculcating professional ethics among employees in the workplace: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies (IJMS) Volume 9, Issue I, 2022*.
- Folkman, J. (2022). *Making yourself indispensable*. River Grove: CA.

- Franco, C. A. (2020). Self-management training for improving job performance: a field experiment involving salespeople. *J. Appl. Psychol.* 85, 361–372.
- Gernalin, J., Bautista, M., & Maguate, G. (2023). Compliance with the code of Conduct and Teaching Performance. *Valley International Journal Digital Library*, 3036-3062.
- Hashim, J. (2018). Competencies acquisition through self-directed learning among Malaysian managers. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 20 (4), 259-271.
- Hayes, B. (2019). Selective sampling and inductive inference: Drawing inferences based on observed and missing evidence. *Cognitive Psychology*, 113
- Hussain, H. & Mohtar, S. (2016). Competency and job performance of non-governmental organization workers: A conceptual framework. *Int.(Lahore)*,28(2), 1903-1914.
- Heinsman, H., de Hoogh, A. H.B., Koopman, P.L., & Van Muijen, J.J. (2018). Commitment, control, and the use of competency management. *Personnel Review*, 37 (6), 609-628.
- Hero, L. M., Lindfors, E., & Taatila, V. (2017). Individual innovation competence: A systematic review and future research agenda. *International Journal of Higher Education*, Vol. 6, No. 5.
- Keban, Y. T. (2018). *Six Strategic Dimensions of Public Administration: Concepts, Theories, and Issues*. Jakarta: Gava Media.
- Lawson T.E., & Limbrick, V. (2016). Critical competencies and developmental experiences for top HR executives. *Human Resource Management*, 35 (1), 67-85.
- Lucia, A. D., & Lepsinger, R. (2019). *The art and science of competency models: Pinpointing critical success factors in organisations*. New York: Pfeiffer.
- Marquez, M. (2022). A correlation study in mapping competencies and employee performance in information technology sector. *Journal of Natural Sciences Edition* Vol: 65 Issue 06.
- Medlin, B., & Green, K.W. (2019). Enhancing performance through goal setting, engagement, and optimism. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 109 (7), 943-956.
- Nassaji, H. (2015). Qualitative and descriptive research: Data type versus data analysis. *Language Teaching Research*, Vol. 19(2) 129–132.
- Navarro, J. (2017). Putting creditors in their rightful place: Corporate governance and business. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 102(1), 21-32.
- Nicdao, J. A. (2021) Assessment of innovation competency: A thematic analysis of upper secondary school teachers' talk. *Journal of Educational Research*, 108(4), 318–330.
- Nufus, T. (2018). Grand Design of the Character of the State Civil Apparatus for the Realization of Bureaucratic Reform. *Adalah*, 2(6d).
- Orbino (2018). *The impact of workplaces and self-management practices on the productivity government workers*. (Unpublished Dissertation). University of East.
- Paler, R. (2018). Contribution of human resource management in creating and sustaining ethical climate in the organizations. *Journal of Human Resource Management* , 5(1), 31-44.
- Pamintuan, G. (2017). Role employees and the service industry: some guidelines for management and research. *Journal of Service Industry Management*, Vol. 7 No. 5, pp. 5-31.
- Pasique, D. A., & Maguate, G. (2023). Challenges and Opportunities Among Educators in The Implementation of Continuing Professional Development. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research (IJFMR)*, 5(4).
- Potnuru, R. K. G., Sahoo, C. & Parle, K. (2020). HRD practices, employee competencies and organizational effectiveness: Role of organizational learning culture. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*. 1-19.
- Prahalad, C. (2021). Strategy as a Field of Study Why Search for a New Paradigm. *Strategic Management Journal*, 5–16.
- Rigor, L. (2019) *Educating for innovation: Sustaining knowledge building at a principle-based innovation in a government office*. Unpublished Dissertation).
- Rodriguez, C. (2016). How management control and job-related characteristics influence the performance of export sales managers. *Journal of Business Research* 60, 1261–1271.

- Strauss, K., Griffin, M. A., & Parker, S. K. (2017). Future work selves: how salient hoped-for identities motivate proactive career behaviors. *J. Appl. Psychol.* 97, 580–598.
- Steve W.J. Kozlowski & Daniel R. Ilgen (2017). Enhancing the Effectiveness of Work Groups and Teams. *Association for Psychological Science*. Volume 7, Issue 3.
- Tamayao, M. (2016). Examining competence factors that encourage innovative behavior by higher education graduate professionals. Unpublished dissertation. Philippine Christian University.
- Tiauzon, M.J., Moyani Jr, G., Bautista, M., & Maguate, G. (2023). Management Skills of Department Heads in Relation to Employees Work Performance. *Valley International Journal Digital Library*, 5327-5334.
- Zenger, J. (2019). *The new extraordinary leader: Turning good managers into great leaders*. McGraw Hill.

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